

occurring. Part of this intensification process will involve improved weed management, yet it is important that such changes do not favor the development of pest nematodes.

References

Koreyem AM. 1993. Observations on the host range and field population patterns of *Hirschmanniella oryzae*, at Kafr-El-Sheikh, Egypt. *Afro-Asian J. Nematol.* 3:50-54.

Mohandas C, Pattanaik NKC, Prasad JS. 1979. Host range of the rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae*. *Indian J. Nematol.* 9:177-178.

Multilocational screening of *Oryza sativa* and *O. glaberrima* for resistance to African rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzivora* in West Africa

C.T. Williams, O. Okhidievbie, West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA), Bouaké, Côte d'Ivoire; M.N. Ukwungwu, National Cereals Research Institute, Bida, Nigeria; D. Dakouo, S. Nacro, INERA Station de Farako-Ba, Bobo-Dioulasso, Burkina Faso; A. Hamadoun, IER/CRRRA, Sikasso, Mali; and S.I. Kamara, Rokupr Rice Research Station, Freetown, Sierra Leone

Resistance to the Asian rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* differs markedly from one location to another because of the existence of genetically distinct biotypes of the pest with differing abilities to overcome resistance genes in their host. To investigate whether the same phenomenon occurs in the African rice gall midge (AfRGM), *Orseolia oryzivora*, the WARDA Integrated Pest Management (IPM) Task Force undertook multilocational screening of *Oryza sativa* and *O. glaberrima* varieties during the wet season at six locations in 1996 and at four sites in 1997. Trial sites were Ogidiga and Gadza in southeast and central Nigeria, respectively; Karfiguéla and Banzon, both in southwest Burkina Faso; Longorola, in south Mali; and Rokupr, in west Sierra Leone.

Rice seed was supplied by Dr. N.Q. Ng of the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture and Dr. B.N. Singh of WARDA. The *sativas* used were a highly susceptible check (ITA306) and African and Asian varieties which, from previous screening in Nigeria, showed significantly lower infestation than ITA306, although most were at least moderately susceptible to rice gall midge. The *glaberrimas* used were all highly to moderately resistant in an earlier screening in Nigeria. Trials were randomized complete block designs with three blocks in which *sativas* and *glaberrimas* were randomized together.

They were carried out in rainfed lowland or irrigated conditions depending on location. Each plot had two rows of 15 hills each, transplanted at 20 × 20 cm with two seedlings hill⁻¹ at 21 d after sowing (DAS). Basal fertilizer application was 40 kg N, P, and K ha⁻¹. A topdressing of 40 kg N ha⁻¹ was applied at 20 d after transplanting

(DAT). AfRGM tiller infestation levels were calculated from gall and tiller counts on 20 hills plot⁻¹ at 63 DAT.

Results showed that AfRGM pressure was high at all locations except Longorola, Mali (Tables 1 and 2). In both years, location had a large effect on AfRGM infestation level on many test entries rela-

Table 1. Percentage of tillers with AfRGM galls at 63 DAT (mean + standard error) at six trial locations, 1996.

Entry ^a	Ogidiga, southeast Nigeria	Gadza, central Nigeria	Karfiguéla, Burkina Faso	Banzon, Burkina Faso	Longorola, Mali	Rokupr, Sierra Leone
<i>sativas</i>						
ITA306 (check)	36.7 + 5.22	27.5 + 3.84	26.9 + 3.67	21.8 + 3.57	6.2 + 0.28	28.2 + 3.05
TOS8144	26.2 + 0.93	9.9 + 2.56	17.1 + 3.04	20.3 + 1.76	5.3 + 1.40	11.8 + 1.32
Eguazankpa	28.7 + 1.14	4.7 + 1.73	21.0 + 2.65	22.2 + 1.68	1.5 + 0.35	3.5 + 0.92
ARC 6618	20.2 + 4.32	8.5 + 2.49	14.5 + 2.12	16.1 + 1.38	3.2 + 0.52	4.8 + 1.27
Nhta 8	18.9 + 4.39	8.9 + 3.96	5.3 + 1.33	12.5 + 1.29	8.2 + 2.27	2.9 + 0.84
Aganni	22.8 + 4.77	5.8 + 1.40	4.4 + 0.52	13.0 + 0.51	2.4 + 1.35	2.4 + 0.66
All <i>sativas</i>	25.6	10.9	14.9	17.7	4.5	8.9
<i>glaberrimas</i>						
TOG7684	0.3 + 0.27	9.1 + 1.23	8.8 + 0.59	12.1 + 1.26	6.7 + 2.53	0.0 + 0.00
TOG6542	1.2 + 1.01	3.3 + 0.98	9.4 + 1.15	13.2 + 2.60	9.5 + 4.53	0.0 + 0.00
TOG6631	0.0 + 0.00	3.7 + 0.53	14.0 + 2.87	12.4 + 1.75	4.3 + 1.23	0.0 + 0.00
TOG6582	0.4 + 0.21	2.8 + 1.04	8.9 + 1.33	14.6 + 5.69	7.2 + 3.09	0.0 + 0.00
TOG7442	0.0 + 0.00	5.3 + 3.65	10.7 + 1.24	6.9 + 1.85	9.6 + 4.00	0.0 + 0.00
TOG7677	0.0 + 0.00	3.8 + 2.08	14.2 + 3.05	7.2 + 0.72	4.7 + 1.26	0.0 + 0.00
TOG6589	0.3 + 0.28	3.1 + 0.57	6.7 + 1.13	11.3 + 1.08	6.5 + 2.94	0.0 + 0.00
TOG6508	0.0 + 0.00	2.7 + 0.89	8.7 + 0.48	11.7 + 1.29	3.7 + 2.43	0.0 + 0.00
TOG7198	0.0 + 0.00	2.3 + 0.54	6.3 + 1.03	11.1 + 1.09	5.7 + 2.41	0.0 + 0.00
TOG6216	0.3 + 0.30	3.2 + 2.00	5.6 + 2.67	4.3 + 2.75	6.0 + 2.50	0.0 + 0.00
All <i>glaberrimas</i>	0.3	3.9	9.3	10.5	6.4	0.0

^a*sativas* and *glaberrimas* are listed in the order of mean infestation level across all sites.

Table 2. Percentage of tillers with AfRGM galls at 63 DAT (mean + standard error) at four trial locations, 1997.

Entry ^a	Ogidiga, southeast Nigeria	Gadza, central Nigeria	Karfiguéla, Burkina Faso	Longorola, Mali
<i>sativas</i>				
ITA306 (check)	24.2 + 1.14	14.5 + 0.67	31.9 + 2.58	3.7 + 0.66
TOS9285	11.7 + 1.32	14.9 + 4.25	21.9 + 2.45	1.8 + 0.57
TOS3563	12.9 + 3.63	8.0 + 1.47	20.0 + 0.91	2.0 + 1.07
TOS11530	12.2 + 1.21	1.8 + 0.65	21.8 + 3.78	4.6 + 1.42
PTB12	13.0 + 3.52	1.5 + 0.42	21.6 + 1.14	3.2 + 0.47
Nhta 8	16.4 + 1.99	9.9 + 5.82	8.7 + 1.89	2.9 + 0.24
TOS3546	11.7 + 1.18	1.7 + 1.02	20.0 + 1.93	2.5 + 0.29
Aganni	10.6 + 1.70	13.0 + 2.47	6.5 + 1.63	2.8 + 0.32
Checkhalopiretal	11.5 + 5.12	5.5 + 2.47	8.9 + 1.51	5.1 + 0.73
Veluthacheera	5.8 + 1.53	3.5 + 1.44	10.9 + 2.32	1.4 + 0.93
TOS14519	2.2 + 0.41	1.1 + 0.85	2.9 + 2.05	2.3 + 0.95
All <i>sativas</i>	12.0	6.9	15.9	2.9
<i>glaberrimas</i>				
TOG6730	0.0 + 0.00	2.0 + 0.42	14.6 + 1.76	2.6 + 0.64
TOG6539	0.0 + 0.00	3.7 + 1.64	12.7 + 3.88	2.7 + 1.04
TOG6472	0.0 + 0.00	1.7 + 0.60	14.6 + 0.40	2.6 + 0.70
TOG7206	0.0 + 0.00	2.1 + 1.15	13.5 + 1.10	2.9 + 0.05
TOG6342	0.0 + 0.00	0.5 + 0.30	14.1 + 0.44	2.7 + 0.82
TOG6489	0.0 + 0.00	0.9 + 0.49	15.0 + 0.83	0.8 + 0.15
TOG6216	0.0 + 0.00	1.1 + 0.32	7.0 + 3.74	1.5 + 0.85
TOG6346	0.0 + 0.00	1.5 + 0.70	5.2 + 2.85	1.9 + 0.51
TOG7106	0.0 + 0.00	0.9 + 0.56	2.0 + 0.95	1.7 + 0.47
All <i>glaberrimas</i>	0.0	1.6	11.0	2.2

^a*sativas* and *glaberrimas* are listed in the order of mean infestation level across all sites.

tive to the check and to each other. Analyses of variance on the arc sine-transformed percentages showed that the interaction between rice variety and location effects was highly significant (1996: $F = 9.89$, df

$= 75$ and 180 , $P < 0.001$; 1997: $F = 7.51$, $df = 57$ and 152 , $P < 0.001$). The most marked difference between locations was in the resistance levels shown by the *glaberrimas* relative to the *sativas*. The *glaberrimas*

were much more resistant than the *sativas* in southeast Nigeria and Sierra Leone. In central Nigeria, most *glaberrimas* were only moderately resistant (1-5% infestation), whereas in Burkina Faso many were susceptible ($>10\%$ infestation) although still, on average, better than the *sativas*. In Mali, there was even less difference between the two species. More data are needed from this location, however, because of the low AfRGM pressure in both years.

Although small differences between locations may be due to environmental effects, such large and consistent variety \times site interactions strongly suggest that AfRGM populations at different locations have genetic differences that affect their abilities to overcome resistance. The results have important implications for future screening and breeding work on AfRGM and highlight the need to screen more *glaberrimas* in Burkina Faso and Mali. Some entries, in particular TOS14519 and TOG7106, appeared to have relatively stable resistance across locations, but these need to be tested further. The WARDA IPM Task Force is continuing this study to identify sources of stable resistance and investigate variation in AfRGM populations.

Resistance to rice stripe virus in differential rice line BL 1

K. Ise, Biological Resources Division, Japan International Research Center for Agricultural Sciences (JIRCAS), 1-2 Ohwashi, Tsukuba, Ibaraki; K. Ishikawa, Virus Control Laboratory, National Agricultural Research Center (NARC), 3-1-1 Kannondai, Tsukuba, Ibaraki, Japan; C. Li, Q. Yang, and C. Ye, Yunnan Academy of Agricultural Science (YAAS), Longtougjie, Kunming, Yunnan, China

Rice stripe virus (RSV) is the most important viral disease of rice in temperate rice-growing countries such as China, Japan, and Korea. Almost all lowland cultivars with RSV resistance in Japan have the *Stvb-i* gene, introduced from the Pakistan indica cultivar Modan. Because the appearance of new strains able to overcome this gene threatens these varieties, sources of resistance to RSV must be diversified.

BL 1 is an elite germplasm line with the blast resistance gene *Pi-b* and has been used as a differential line for testing the pathogenicity of blast fungus. It was bred by backcrossing the Japanese cultivar Norin 25 with the Indonesian cultivar Tjina to introduce blast resistance from indica to japonica.

Tjina, BL 1, and F_1 plants from a cross between Nipponbare and BL 1

showed no symptoms in a field test for RSV resistance, although the average infection percentage of susceptible cultivars Nipponbare and Norin 25 was 92.6% (Table 1). BL 1 and its donor parent for blast resistance, Tjina, were highly resistant to or symptomatically tolerant of RSV infection in the field. In a test for resistance to the RSV vector, the smaller brown planthopper (SBPH), *Laodelphax striatellus*, the total